

Towards Continuous Bridge Inspection with Vehicle-to-Infrastructure Communication

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Abstract:

Establishing a continuous bridge inspection framework would contribute to the safety, resilience, and efficiency of the transportation system. In this paper, we propose a continuous bridge inspection framework that leverages vehicle-to-infrastructure communication and road vehicles with a front-view camera. We report the design of two key components towards establishing such a framework: 1) A communication protocol that enables vehicle-to-infrastructure communication for bridge inspections. 2) A crack detection model tailored for the vehicle front-view camera. We report the performance of these components based on experimental data, and project further research directions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bridge monitoring and maintenance are ubiquitous in today's transportation system, as they directly affect roadway safety and traffic efficiency. Out of all the components, bridge deck maintenance accounts for more than 50% of the total bridge maintenance cost (Kong et al., 2022, Yang, Ibrahim et al., 2024, Omar, 2022). Visible surface damage, such as joint cracking, grout spalling, or reflective cracking, is an early indicator of structural degradation. Routine inspections are key to identifying these early signs of damage, allowing preventive repair and maintaining bridge integrity. Currently, the predominant inspection method remains manual inspection, which is labor-intensive and costly.

With the help of artificial intelligence, more autonomous platforms have been developed, including drones (Hu et al., 2024, Song et al., 2025, Ranyal et al., 2022) and purposefully designed robots & vehicles. While these platforms can provide reliable detection accuracy, they still have limitations, such as battery life constraints, high operational costs, and potential traffic disruptions from repeated inspection runs due to the sensing range and camera viewing angles. As a result, there remains a significant gap in developing a continuous, autonomous, and cost-effective bridge deck monitoring framework that minimizes regular traffic interruptions. Road vehicles with advanced sensing (e.g., front-view camera), communication (Cellular-Vehicle-to-everything, or C-V2X), computing, and automation technologies have become increasingly common. These capabilities enable road vehicles to participate in bridge inspections by checking early visible signs. In this work, we seek to leverage connected vehicles with forward-facing cameras and CV2X technologies for continuous bridge deck monitoring. In our proposed framework, illustrated in Figure 1, a roadside unit (RSU) mounted on the infrastructure (e.g., bridges) communicates with OBUs installed on the passing vehicles. On the vehicle side, the OBU coordinates with the sensor flows to streamline detection from real-time image fusion and sends the results back to the RSU to close the loop of the whole infrastructure-guided inspection pipeline.

Figure 1 Overview of the Vehicle-to-Infrastructure Communication Based Continuous Bridge Inspection (Bridge figure source: [North Carolina Department of Transportation \(NCDOT\)](#))

While leveraging vehicles for bridge inspection can reduce concerns about traffic interruption, it creates a challenge for the detection model. Existing crack detection models are trained on benchmark datasets such as CrackTree260 (Zou et al., 2018), where crack images are captured from a top-down camera angle. Current leading detection models, such as DeepCrack (Zou et al., 2018) and LESCFormer (Chen et al., 2023) performs well on the benchmark test, but both show noticeable performance degradation when

operating under real-world traffic scenarios, from which the input images are taken, with cracks appearing small in the image frames.

In this paper, we briefly present two contributions to address these challenges: first is customizing a reliable communication protocol between the RSU and OBU such that it can coordinate with the information sharing not only limits to the vehicle status, but also the image of the crack masks; second is adopting the detection models to improve the performance on the vehicle’s field of view.

2. BRIDGE INSPECTION FRAMEWORK

The proposed pipeline is built based on the communication between the roadside unit (RSU) and the onboard unit (OBU) mounted on the vehicle. It comprises three stages: from the moment the OBU receives a detection request from the RSU to the moment the RSU receives the estimated crack length and the crack mask image. The vehicle-side pipeline's underlying software architecture is implemented using Python-based ROS2 nodes integrated with the Autoware software stack on the vehicle, which streamlines modular design and real-time sharing of vehicle information among different sensing components.

2.1 Pipeline Workflow

There are three stages between the moment the RSU sends a detection request to the OBU and the OBU sends the crack mask image and the estimated crack length back to the RSU, c.f., Figure 1. In Stage I, the RSU sends the request to the OBU node, and the OBU receives the region of interest to proceed with the inspection. This stage does not include any data logging, as the distance between the vehicle and the crack may be too large to meet the crack-estimation resolution requirement. In Stage II, the vehicle decides the image logging time using the data fusion started in Stage I. Once in the desired range and the crack is clearly visible in the image frame, it starts logging images and simultaneously computing the theoretical region of focus for each data fusion timestamp. The cropping information, along with the raw images, is asynchronously saved to ensure optimal synchronization in Stage III. In Stage III, the logged cropping coordinates are first synchronized with the corresponding raw images, which are then cropped and fed into the detection node for inference. Once the request is addressed, the OBU packs the detection results and image masks, then sends them to the RSU.

Figure 2. Communication Protocol

2.2 Vehicle-To-Infrastructure Communication Protocol

We propose a vehicle-to-infrastructure communication protocol illustrated in Figure 2. During detection, the RSU always initiates communication. It first confirms whether the OBU is within communication range and establishes a one-to-one result-checking channel for detection updates. On the other hand, the OBU receives the RSU request and starts parallel tasking: it continuously monitors the vehicle's result updates while simultaneously broadcasting the vehicle's status to the lower-level vehicle interface for decision-making. Once the vehicle enters Stage III, it transmits the inference crack mask image, along with the estimated crack length, in chunks from the OBU back to the RSU. The communication protocol is implemented on top of the API provided by the CV2X vendor. Such an API allows vehicles to share their status (via what standard) with other OBUs and RSUs within the communication range, and this feature

can also be packaged as a ROS2 message to be subscribed to by the vehicle control interface for further decision-making.

We verify the performance of the proposed design in an experiment to understand the success rate, bandwidth, and transmission time. We attempted 10 rounds of image transmission, each comprising 3 sets of images of different sizes, while the vehicle moved within a 200-meter perimeter around the RSU at a fixed location. The results in Table 1. While we can report that 100% success rate (i.e., no package loss), the bandwidth is limited, especially for large images. It would not be feasible to send a full image of the deck surface (>500 kB) between OBUs and RSUs within the detection window and transmission range (<20 seconds and <1km). Thus, we will focus on crack length reports in our future study and defer the full image results report to future CV2X technologies.

Table 1. Communication Payload and Performance

Image Size [kB]	Transmission	Transmission Time
	Time OBU to RSU (Mean/STD) [ms]	RSU to OBU (Mean/STD) [ms]
4.75	176 / 2.5	159 / 24
18.2	409 / 23	333 / 124
323	5626 / 167	3977 / 450

3. CRACK DETECTION MODEL

In this section, we explain how we adapt the state-of-the-art (SoA) crack detection models to ensure the pipeline is able to recognize the cracks on the pavement surface and further estimate the length of the it. We selected two SoA models, DeepCrack and LESCFormer, based on their relatively small training sets, high accuracy, and reproducibility (Ma et al., 2025). We note that our focus is on adapting the models to the vehicle’s front-view image input, rather than improving the benchmark performance of any of the models. We used the DeepCrack (Zou et al., 2018) as the pre-trained weight, but did more refinement on the LESCFormer (Chen et al., 2023) model.

3.1 Real-time Performance Baseline

We collect a dataset of 443 images recorded under diverse operational conditions, including different lighting, glare, motion blur, and asphalt textures. The dataset is split into 343 training images (denoted RT 343) and 100 test images (denoted RT 100); the dataset is available here along with the code at https://github.com/CHELabUB/cav_road_crack_detection. In Table 1, we compared our reproduced results for the LESCFormer model with the original reported performance and with its performance on our RT100. While both DeepCrack and LESCFormer achieved strong benchmark performance, we observed significant degradation when switching from the benchmark to the real-time testing set.

Table 2. Performance comparison between CRKWH100 testing set and RT100 testing set

Model	Testing Data	ODS F1	AP
LECSFormer (Reported)	CRKWH100	0.9530	Not provided
LESCFormer (Retrained)	CRKWH100	0.9184	0.4973
LECSFormer (Retrained)	RT100	0.3744	0.1225

3.2 Improvement on Model and Real-time Performance

To address the performance degradation in a dataset composed of real-time images, we conducted an ablation study. Using the pre-trained DeepCrack model as a baseline, we unified our base training set by adopting CrackTree260 to ensure a fair comparison.

We first investigated the impact of data augmentation by applying different augmentation strategies to CrackTree260. Specifically, we used original augmentation methods described in the literature, denoted as V2, an enhanced version of V2 with additional transformations denoted as V3, and our crack-density-aware augmentation method as V1.

From the results in Table 2, we observed that although augmentation improves overall performance, the scale range of the improved F1 score is still not satisfying. We further retrained the models with a mix of RT343 and original CrackTree260 to further evaluate the effectiveness of the augmentation methods V1 and V3. The remaining 100 images were deployed as the Real-Time testing set (RT100). The results show that incorporating the RT343 training set achieved at most 89% improvement over LECSFormer trained on CrackTree260 without image augmentation.

Table 3. Ablation Study: Real-Time Performance (ODS F1)

Training Configuration	ODS (RT100)
Baseline Models	
DeepCrack (Pre-trained)	0.3374
LECSFormer (CrackTree260 – No Augmentation)	0.2923
Augmentation Effect (CrackTree260)	
DeepCrack Augmentation (V2)	0.3287
Enhanced DeepCrack Augmentation (V3)	0.3411
Advanced Augmentation (V1)	0.3744
Front View Camera Image Integration	
CrackTree260 + RT343 (V1)	0.5267
CrackTree260 + RT343 (V3)	0.5522

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a framework for a continuous infrastructure-oriented pavement crack detection pipeline. Specifically, we explained our approaches to address two obstacles: the RSU-to-OBU communication protocol and model adaptation to the vehicle front-camera view. Our results confirmed the feasibility of the communication protocol. We also reported improvements of up to 89% on our carefully prepared real-time testing set, RT100, for the crack detection model relative to the baseline. For more details, please refer to our future publications (Xiao et al., 2026). Ongoing work includes continuing to refine the detection pipeline, improving the robustness of the detection algorithm, and integrating detection with automated vehicle motion (Xiao and He, 2025)

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